

EFFECT OF FRIGID TEMPERATURES ON THE DYNAMIC PROPERTIES OF FIBER REINFORCED MARINE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Fibre reinforced composites, such as carbon reinforced vinyl-ester, are increasingly being considered as practical structural materials for current and new classes of civilian and military naval crafts. These crafts are expected to operate in the world at large (from the equator to the poles) and service under a variety of harsh conditions. To ensure the durability and functionality of these crafts, composites used in their construction should endure by design a wide range of complex and severe loadings as well as harsh marine environmental conditions. Therefore, it is instrumental to characterize and understand the effects of harsh marine environments on the behaviour and failure properties of fibre reinforced marine composites. Accordingly, this work is focused on investigating the synergistic degrading effects of frigid temperatures and moisture on the mechanical and failure properties of carbon reinforced vinyl-ester composites under quasi-static and dynamic loading conditions. For the quasi-static cases, this work utilizes ASTM D790-10 based 3-point bend setup to apply flexural loading on composite specimens subjected to moisture and frigid temperatures. On the other hand, for the dynamic case, this work plans to utilize multiple modified Kolsky apparatuses integrated with custom-made liquid nitrogen cooled chambers and high speed imaging to investigate the effect of moisture and frigid temperatures on the dynamic properties. The latter experimental arrangements allow for performing dynamic tension, bending and penetration/perforation tests under controlled frigid conditions and allow for characterizing the effect of frigid temperatures on the ductility/brittleness, energy absorbing capacity, toughness and critical penetration velocity of fibre reinforced marine composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are increasingly being considered as a popular alternative to conventional metallic materials in new classes of marine vessels (e.g. Zumwalt-Class Destroyer [1]) due to their lower density, higher specific strength and stiffness, reduced radar signature, better corrosion resistance as compared to metals [2] and their potential for exhibiting unique and application-tailored properties through polymer synthesis, functionalization and nano-reinforcing (e.g. [3]). In addition, the growing shift towards fiber polymer composites has been motivated by the strive of navies and militaries worldwide to increase maneuverability, fuel efficiency, structural and operational performance (e.g. increased payload, stability, and stealth) of naval crafts and reduce their acquisition and maintenance costs [4].

Even with the proven utility and great potential of fiber reinforced composites as marine structural materials, there remain unresolved lingering questions regarding FRP composites long-term properties, performance, durability and structural integrity in harsh environmental conditions [5]. These questions

stem from the limited understanding of the deleterious effects of the cooperative harsh environmental elements that composite materials can be exposed to and adversely affected by in marine applications [6]. However, answering these questions is instrumental to ensuring the reliability of composite marine crafts and accelerating the wide-spread implementation of FRP composites in critical applications.

Composite marine crafts will be subjected to harsh environmental elements including UV radiation, sea water (with salt and chemicals) and temperature extremes (high to frigid (0~-50C)[5, 7]). These elements, individually and synergistically, through various mechanisms can gradually detriment the mechanical properties of FRP composites, but with time, the negative effects can accumulate, and after long-term exposure, the degradation in composites' mechanical properties can be significant [5, 8, 9]. However, any potential degradation in the mechanical properties should be quantified, understood and predicted as it will affect the structural reliability and integrity of composite marine crafts, and it should be incorporated in maintenance plans and schedules. The predictability of deterioration with long-term exposure to harsh environments is even more critical for composite marine warships as they are often subjected to significant loads such as hydrodynamic forces due to slamming and low velocity impacts due to interaction with floating objects. In addition, they are expected to withstand by design impulsive and shock hydrodynamic forces generate by underwater explosions.

Currently, the process of designing reliable and enduring composite marine crafts is instrumentally dependent upon two elements: I) The availability of experimental based material constitutive models capable of accounting for deterioration in the structural properties of FRP composites due to long-term exposure to marine environments, and II) The utilization of protective coatings (epoxy or ester based [10]) to prevent and limit environmental based degradation from significantly affecting the structural properties (e.g. stiffness, strength toughness) of FRP composites. However, these coatings are susceptible to wear, corrosion, environmental degradation and can become damaged due to normal use or inadvertent activities, resulting in exposing fiber reinforced composites to harsh marine environmental elements which can degrade the exposed composite. Therefore, even with protective coatings, to ensure the structural integrity of composite naval crafts and warships, it is instrumental to establish a detailed and predictive understanding of the interaction between the effects of both severe loading conditions and harsh environmental elements on the mechanical properties of FRP composites in quasi-static and dynamic loadings.

For FRP composites, the knowledge-base as well as the availability and maturity of constitutive models that account for environmental degradation are limited; in particular, with respect to the synergistic degradation effects of marine environmental elements at frigid temperatures (0~-50C), under both quasi-static and dynamic loadings (e.g., impact and slamming). This synergistic degradation scenario with UV, sea water and frigid temperatures, particularly for dynamic loadings, is among the least characterized and analyzed but potentially qualifies to be amongst the most critical scenarios. This scenario is the main focus of the long-term goals of this work. This scenario is realized when a composite marine craft operating in frigid conditions, with pre-degraded composites due to exposure to UV and sea water, is subjected to impact or excessive hydrodynamic forces due to impact with floating ice, slamming or under water explosions. The key for composites to withstand impulsive and excessive transient loadings is to exhibit resilience, compliance and toughness. However, the cooperative deleterious effects of frigid temperatures, UV and sea water are anticipated to significantly reduce the toughness and resilience as well as increase the brittleness of the exposed composite, which under dynamic or impulsive loading might lead to catastrophic failure; particularly, if the degradation in mechanical properties is not accurately anticipated by the composite marine craft designers. This scenario is not limited to Polar Regions with severe frigid temperatures; it can occur in many parts of the world as an air temperature of -40C can be realized, for example, in the great lakes, northeastern or northwestern US regional waters during the winter season.

The aforementioned anticipation, that the cooperative deleterious effects of frigid temperatures, UV radiation and sea water can be significant and more pronounced as compared to their individual effects, is based on the current state-of-the-art understanding of the degradation mechanisms associated with each of the individual environmental elements. However, such analysis allows only for establishing qualitative predictions and cannot quantitatively predict the level and extent of the synergistic damage in terms of mechanical properties. A synoptic analysis of the known environmental based degradation mechanisms shows that FRP composites are sensitive to UV radiation, moisture, temperature and

chemicals, but the adverse effect of these elements can be more severe and harder to anticipate when they act in a combined manner [8, 9, 11]. Generally, it is observed that moisture diffusion can cause matrix hydrolysis and plasticization and fiber-matrix debonding which knocks down the FRP composites strength and toughness properties. The adverse effect of moisture is increased at elevated temperatures due to the increase in water diffusion (e.g. with an increase in temperature from 50C to 70C, moisture absorption by carbon epoxy composite can increase by more than 100% [12]). UV radiation is observed to cause increase in brittleness and surface micro-cracking due to photo-oxidation and molecular chains scissions [13], which increase the brittleness of FRP composites and decrease their toughness. In addition, micro-cracks can act as sources for stress concentrations and can promote crack initiation and propagation [13]. Also, micro-cracks caused by UV radiation can facilitate moisture diffusion thus amplifying the adverse effect of moisture. Enhanced moisture absorption due to UV and elevated temperatures also worsens the effect of any chemicals present in sea water, as enhanced moisture absorption allows for deeper chemical penetration and increased concentration. In the case of carbon fibers, moisture in the presence of metals and salt water can damage the fibers through a galvanic reaction [5]. The aforementioned degradation mechanisms can negatively affect, to different extents, reinforcing fibers, matrix material and fiber-matrix interfaces; therefore, they can negatively affect a wide range of mechanical properties including stiffness, strength, fatigue and fracture toughness. The effects of these mechanisms can be amplified at frigid temperatures as frigid temperatures will superpose an additional reduction in compliance and toughness. In addition, the absorbed moisture could freeze, and with thermal expansion mismatch between the moisture phase and the matrix phase, frozen moisture could cause further damage and fiber-matrix delamination. Naturally, as all aforementioned elements (UV, moisture, and frigid temperatures) are cooperatively acting to reduce the toughness, strength, compliance and resilience of the exposed FRP composites, their dynamic properties and structural integrity at high rates of deformation will be adversely affected. However, the level of the anticipated deleterious cooperative effects cannot be predicted due to the lack of experimental data that describes the synergistic effects of UV, sea water, frigid temperatures and high rates of deformation. The aforementioned overview aimed to illustrate the significance of synergistic degradation effects, which this work aims to experimentally investigate and quantify.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The material used in this work is Carbon-fiber reinforced vinyl-ester unidirectional composite laminate. Laminates are acquired from Graphtek LLC as sheets and cut using diamond wet saw into rectangular specimens with fibers either running along their length (i.e. longitudinal) or width (i.e. transverse). Longitudinal specimens are loaded along their fiber direction while the transverse specimens are loaded along a direction perpendicular to the fibers. Thus, experimental results describe the composite laminate longitudinal and transverse mechanical properties.

In reality, the interaction between frigid temperatures and moisture can follow infinite scenarios. One element might lead the other, they can occur together, or they can alternate. The time span and frequency of each element can change dramatically over a period of time. Thus, to provide insights into the interaction between frigid temperature and moisture, only few carefully selected interactive scenarios need to be investigated. As it is anticipated that the composite marine craft will be subjected to cycles of frigid temperatures and exposure to moisture, this work investigates the following scenarios:

a) Moisture exposure (wet environment)

Composite laminates were cut into large pieces and placed in water filled containers. Specimens remained submerged in water at room temperature ($19^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$) for a total of 2760 hours. The large composite specimens were then cut into smaller specimens (3in long and 0.5in wide) (i.e., test ready specimens) and tested within an hour from the moment they were taken out of the water containers. Specimens were cut to larger pieces first to limit water diffusion from the sides of the specimens.

b) Exposure to cycles of frigid temperatures and wet environments (freeze-wet thaw)

Composite specimens were submerged in water at room temperature ($19^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 1272 and then subjected to freeze-thaw cycles. To freeze the specimens, a thermofisher laboratory freezer was used. Specimens were removed from the water, dried with a tissue, placed in the freezer and

kept for 5 hours at $(-21^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C})$. The 5 hours period was chosen to ensure that the diffused moisture inside specimens reaches a frozen state. After freezing specimens were taken out from the freezer and submerged in water at room temperature (for 3 to 6 hours) to thaw. Thawing in water guaranteed that specimens will not dry out (defused moisture inside specimens is maintained). The freeze-thaw cycles were repeated and four groups of specimens were prepared. These groups were subjected to 25, 50, 75 and 100 freeze-wet thaw cycles, respectively.

- c) Exposure to cycles of dry environments and frigid temperatures (freeze-dry thaw cycles)

To provide insights into the interaction between moisture and frigid temperatures, and to enable conducting comparisons between freeze-thaw cycles with and without the presence of moisture, freeze-dry thaw specimen conditioning was performed concurrently with the freeze-wet thaw conditioning. Accordingly, dry composite specimens were placed in freezing conditions with the wet composite specimens. However, in the thawing phase, while the wet thaw specimens were placed to thaw in a wet environment, the dry thaw specimens were placed on a counter top on a tissue and allowed to thaw at room temperature. Once the wet specimens were put back in the freezer, they were again accompanied by the dry specimens. Eventually as for the freeze-wet thaw cycles, four groups for composite specimens conditioned under freeze-dry thaw cycles were prepared. These groups were subjected to 25, 50, 75 and 100 freeze-thaw cycles respectively.

- d) Room temperature and moisture conditions (benchmark)

These specimens were meant to be used as a benchmark and were kept in dry conditions (lab environment) under room temperature $(19^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C})$.

All conditioned specimens were tested under flexural loading conditions that minimize transverse shear stresses according to ASTM D790-10 standard. Test setup is shown in Fig. 1

Figure 1: 3-point bend test setup.

Tests were performed using an electromechanical MTS (Criterion Model 43). For each specimen the load and displacement data were reported by the machine. Force-displacement data were used to compute the failure strength, failure strain and the effective modulus. Data reduction which followed ASTM D790-10 assumed that failure occurred at the top surface (tension). Based on ASTM D790-10 standard, the failure strength is computed as

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3PL}{2bd^2} \quad (1)$$

such that P is the max load, L is the support span, b is the width of the specimen, d is the thickness of the specimen.

3 RESULTS

Force-displacement curves (from 3-point bend) for all specimens described in the previous section exhibited the following sequence: a linear response that ends at the collapse load (maximum force), sudden drop in the load carrying capacity (to about one half of the original load carrying capacity), continuous and gradual drop in the load carrying capacity with further loading. Figure 2 presents load-

Figure 2: Load-displacement data.

displacement data for the 25 and 100 freeze-thaw cycles (dry and wet). This figure demonstrates the observed trends, highlights the repeatability of the tests and shows the behavior at and beyond the initial failure. These results, in general, show that increasing number of freeze-thaw cycles reduces the failure strength. In addition, with moisture, the effect of frigid temperatures appears to be amplified. For instance, by studying the load-displacement for the specimens subjected to 100 cycles of freeze-wet thaw, one sees that this scenario is the most catastrophic. Interestingly, the sudden drop in the load carrying capacity stops roughly at the 250 N level for most specimens. This indicates that while the initial failure occurs at the damaged surface of the loaded specimen, the inner core of the specimens remain an undamaged.

To investigate the effects of the failure strength of the composite, Eqn. (1) was used to determine the failure strength at the maximum loading (from load-displacement curves). Resulting failure strength values are presented in Fig. 3

Figure 3 shows that freeze-thaw cycling results in significant drop in the failure strength of the composite, particularly in wet environments. It is expected that freeze-thaw cycles will cause internal damage in the matrix and the matrix fiber interfaces due to the thermal expansion mismatch between the fiber and resin phases. In wet environments as water diffuses into the matrix and along damaged fiber-matrix interfaces, freeze-thaw cycles can be associated with amplified damage; particularly as defused moisture can freeze and result in additional thermal mismatch related stresses. However, these results remain preliminary and additional results and analysis (which are focus of our ongoing work) will provide more insights into the derivative effects of frigid temperature and moisture on fiber composites.

Figure 3: Failure strength variation with freeze-thaw cycles

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper reports on the preliminary results of an experimental work focused on investigating the synergistic effects of frigid temperatures and moisture on the mechanical and failure properties of fiber reinforced marine composites. Results focused on the effect of freeze-thaw cycles and illustrated that freeze-thaw cycles in dry or wet environments would result in significant negative effects. However, in wet environments, the negative effects are more severe, indicating that moisture and frigid temperatures have a cooperative damaging mechanism.

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